

The Evolution of Gender in English: From Proto-Indo-European to Modern English through Old and Middle English

Saul Hoffmann [850849]

Dipartimento di Scienze del Linguaggio - Glottodidattica
Università Ca' Foscari

A.A. 2013/2014*

*Final paper for the *Filologia Germanica 1* course [LM0350] held by Prof. Marina Buzzoni.

Contents

Introduction	3
1 Gender in Proto-Indo-European	4
1.1 Animate vs. inanimate	4
1.2 A three-gender system	4
2 Gender in Old English	5
2.1 The gender attribution system	5
2.2 Divergence from the system	5
2.3 Linguistic borrowings	7
2.3.1 Gender preservation	7
2.3.2 Gender change	8
3 Gender in Middle English	9
3.1 From Old English to Middle English	9
3.2 Switch from grammatical to natural gender	10
3.3 Gender in personal pronouns	11
4 Gender in Modern English	14
4.1 Animation and reification	14
Conclusions	16

Introduction

“Genders are classes of nouns reflected in the behavior of associated words”¹ The regularity of application of gender-assigning rules has been questioned in the last years. For example, in semantic systems like English, besides animateness and sex, also other factors play an important role in the determining of the gender of a referent.

In the following sentences, taken from a corpus of English spoken in Los Angeles and Buffalo²: the third person singular pronouns *he* and *she* are used to refer to inanimate objects:

[Woman talking about a chair]

He has lost his leg, so don't sit on him unless you like the floor.

[Man talking about a bike he has owned for years]

She has just about had it.

As we will see, this same behavior could already be observed in Old English, and has puzzled for many years scholars trying to reconstruct gender assignment rules in the forerunner of Modern English.

In this work we will see how gender has changed during the centuries, starting out with the reconstructed Proto-Indo-European animate vs. inanimate opposition (somewhat describable as “masculine+feminine” vs. “neuter”). Then, the emergence of a third gender (namely feminine) led to a rearrangement of the system, switching to a three-gender one: we are talking now of grammatical gender, which was the way Old English chose to use. The subsequent inexorable loss of morphology (together with other factors, as we will see later) led to another resetting of the criterion: already Middle English shows to adopt natural gender, which is what Modern English uses. And the transformations are still ongoing...

¹Hockett (1958), as quoted in Greville G. Corbett (1991). *Gender*. Cambridge Textbooks in Linguistics. Cambridge University Press.

²Andrew Pawley (2002). “Using He and She for Inanimate Referents in English: Questions of Grammar and World View”. In: *Ethnosyntax : Explorations in Grammar and Culture*. Ed. by N. J. Enfield. Oxford University Press, pp. 110–137.

1 Gender in Proto-Indo-European

1.1 Animate vs. inanimate

Proto-Indo-European originally only distinguished two genders. The *animate* gender contained mostly adult human referents (children are usually still neuter in modern Indo-European languages), together with other entities able of “acting” in some way (moving, for example). The *inanimate* gender instead, simply contained the residue.

Lazzeroni³ states that many of the synonymic words found in today’s Indo-European languages have their origin in the Proto-Indo-European original distinction between agent/subject and patient/object, as can be seen in the following examples⁴:

Fire:

Latin	<i>ignis</i>		Greek	<i>pyr</i>	
Sanskrit	<i>agnih</i>	masculine	Hittite	<i>pahhur</i>	neuter
Russian	<i>ogon’</i>		English	<i>fire</i>	

Water:

Latin	<i>aqua</i>		Greek	<i>hydōr</i>	
Sanskrit	<i>āpas</i> (waters)	feminine	Hittite	<i>watar</i>	neuter
Gothic	<i>ahva</i> (river)		English	<i>water</i>	

1.2 The switch to a three-gender system

According to Luraghi⁵, when feminine emerged (firstly with a “collective” meaning) the whole classification was re-analysed basing the distinction on the gender of the referents, so that the two kinds of animated entities were divided between masculine and feminine gender (which thus came to contain a large amount of abstract words), whereas neuter (lat. *ne+uter*, “neither”) kept conveying a static/inanimate meaning. The loss of this animation-based distinction in modern languages made them choose one of the two possible variants between the words listed above, because they had become uselessly redundant.

³Romano Lazzeroni (2002). “Ruoli tematici e genere grammaticale: un aspetto della morfossintassi indoeuropea?” In: *Archivio glottologico italiano* 87.1, pp. 3–19.

⁴Found in Silvia Luraghi (2006). “La nascita del genere femminile in indoeuropeo”. In: *Linguaggio e genere: grammatica e usi*. Ed. by S. Luraghi and A. Olita. Carocci.

⁵Ibid.

2 Gender in Old English

In Old English we still have three genders, but their attribution to substantives is not uniform. In the past, the irregularity of gender attribution –widespread both synchronically and diachronically⁶– was ascribed to chance, while nowadays it has been established that

“Copyists are for sure responsible of many text manipulations, sometimes caused by the changed linguistic situation, but generally one tends to blame them too much.”⁷

In fact, we have to acknowledge that the usage of more genders for the same word must have been caused by some other reason.

2.1 The gender attribution system

Here is a rapid overview of the “standard” gender attribution system in Old English. One can find the gender of a word considering the following features:

- Belonging to a certain inflectional class;
- Presence of certain derivational suffixes: e.g. *-et* usually refers to neuter (*bænet* ‘fire’), *-ung* to feminine (*hræglung* ‘clothes’), and *-dom* to masculine (*cynedom* ‘reign’).⁸

Anyway, it should be remembered that gender is usually not easy to infer from morphology, because the endings are almost always ambiguous (besides *-as*, which is always masculine plural).

2.2 Divergence from the system

When a word occurs with two different genders, the explanation resides in one of the two following kinds of divergence:

1. Conflict between grammatical and natural gender;
2. Apparent arbitrary gender occurrence.

⁶Letizia Vezzosi (2008). “Come la linguistica generale e la tipologia possono aprire nuovi scenari: il caso dell’assegnazione del genere in anglosassone”. In: *La linguistica germanica oggi: bilanci e prospettive*. Ed. by Claudia Händl and Chiara Benati.

⁷“Gli amanuensi sono certo responsabili di molte manipolazioni dei testi, connesse talvolta anche con una situazione linguistica mutata, ma in genere si tende a colpevolizzarli un po’ troppo.” My translation from Raffaella Del Pezzo (1994). “Diacronia della lingua gotica?” In: *Annali Istituto Orientale di Napoli-Sezione Germanica* 4.1-2, pp. 9–22.

⁸Examples from Vezzosi, “Come la linguistica generale e la tipologia possono aprire nuovi scenari: il caso dell’assegnazione del genere in anglosassone”.

Case 1 is easily explained:⁹

- Inside the nominal phrase natural agreement is rare but not impossible, especially if the referent is human. E.g. *ðio wif*
- Outside the nominal phrase agreement is actually quite frequent. E.g. *wyrc þe nu ænne arc ... gehref hit eall*

According to Corbett,¹⁰ the more anaphoric pronoun and antecedent are distant, the easier it is for natural agreement to appear. The hierarchy he deduced is the following:

attribute → predicate → relative pronoun → personal pronoun

A modern example of this can be seen in German, where *das Mädchen*(n.) 'the girl' can be referred back to, both with the neuter pronoun *Es* or the natural, feminine one *Sie*. The sentence "The girl has come home from school. She is now doing her homework", can thus be rendered both with:

- Das Mädchen (n.) ist aus der Schule gekommen. Es (n.) macht jetzt seine (n.) Hausaufgaben.
- Das Mädchen (n.) ist aus der Schule gekommen. Sie (f.) macht jetzt ihre (f.) Hausaufgaben.¹¹

Case 2 is more complex, since it refers also to words with inanimate referents, therefore without a sexual connotation. The reasons of gender divergence can be the following:¹²

- Partly because of copyists' errors (with the *caveat* we already mentioned above);
- Contacts with other peoples;¹³
- Phonetic erosion of the word's endings;¹⁴

⁹Examples from Vezzosi, "Come la linguistica generale e la tipologia possono aprire nuovi scenari: il caso dell'assegnazione del genere in anglosassone".

¹⁰Corbett, *Gender*.

¹¹From Wikipedia: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Grammatical_gender

¹²As listed in Vezzosi, "Come la linguistica generale e la tipologia possono aprire nuovi scenari: il caso dell'assegnazione del genere in anglosassone".

¹³"the confusion results from a population that did not know the original system well" J. D. Collins (1990). "Natural Gender Vs. Grammatical Gender in Old English". In: *16th LACUS Forum*. Ed. by Linguistic Association of Canada and the United States, pp. 481–490.

¹⁴"Gender is initially (Proto-Indo-European) overt, i.e. the morphological shape of words indicates directly what gender a given word has. Because this is typically marked on the ending and these endings are lost, gender either becomes more and more associated with semantic subgroups of the vocabulary, or with phonological or morphological clues, or with a combination of these." Frederick W. Schwink (2004). *The Third Gender : Studies in the Origin and History of Germanic Grammatical Gender*. Winter.

- Dialectal varieties;¹⁵
- A \pm particularizing trait (aspectual function).¹⁶

2.3 Gender assignment in linguistic borrowings

As Welna points out¹⁷, Old English received loanwords from many other languages, including –but probably not limited to– Latin, Scandinavian, Celtic, Greek and Old French. All these words had to be grammatically adapted to the borrowing language, and of course gender reflects this fact. We have cases in which the original gender is preserved, and others in which it has changed in every possible combination: feminine to masculine, neuter to feminine, and so on.

2.3.1 Gender preservation

Welna¹⁸ identifies seven different gender determiners, which must have been regularly applying masculine, feminine, and neuter gender to loan-nouns, thus making gender attribution more stable. They are the following:

Sex Of course this only applies to masculine and feminine nouns. Nonetheless, all borrowed words marked for sex kept their gender when accepted into Old English;

Cover term It refers to the tendency of assigning the same gender to all loan-nouns belonging to the same semantic field. E.g. feminine gender assigned to all plants;

Semantic equivalent This is quite straight-forward: if the borrowed word can be associated to a word in the borrowing language, then the gender reflects this association;

Affixes If the ending of the loan-words contains affixes that in Old English are marked with sex, particularly V(vowel)+*r*, V+*l*, V+*k* are masculine; V+*n* feminine and V+(*e*)*t* are neuter;

¹⁵Peter Kitson (1990). “On Old English Nouns of More than One Gender”. In: *English Studies* 71, pp. 185–221.

¹⁶“A noun would be of animated gender when it expresses an agent or beneficiary or subject, it would be of neuter gender if patient or grammatical object.” Vezzosi, “Come la linguistica generale e la tipologia possono aprire nuovi scenari: il caso dell’assegnazione del genere in anglosassone”.

¹⁷Jerzy Welna (1980). “On gender change in linguistic borrowing (Old English)”. In: *Historical Morphology*. Trends in Linguistics. Studies and Monographs [TiLSM]. De Gruyter, pp. 399–420.

¹⁸Ibid.

Resemblance of stem or word final element Just the formal resemblance is important, not the meaning;

Similarity of the inflectional morpheme It is the case of latin *comēta* (m.), which ends with *-a*, marker of masculine in Old English (therefore OE *comēta*);

Characteristic endings Latin endings *-us*, *-a*, *-um* marking respectively masculine, feminine, and neuter are known to the educated writer and therefore treated as such.

In the case of sex distinction or grammatical endings, gender assignment takes place in L_1 and have to be considered cases of external identification. All other cases are instead internal (to Old English).

2.3.2 Gender change

Latin words are the majority of the borrowings, and they tend to retain their original gender. This is most probably due to the fact that Latin loans were of a learned status, so that who introduced them was fully aware of their grammatical gender. This is the reason why most of the Latin words ending with *-a* (a morpheme which usually is feminine) remained feminine also in Old English, even if in the latter this ending typically marked the masculine.

It should be noted, though, that while most masculine Latin words stayed masculine, and one-third of the feminine words changed gender, two-thirds of the neuter words did.¹⁹ There is in fact a tendency to eliminate neuter and –to a lesser degree– feminine, in favour of masculine.

¹⁹Welna, “On gender change in linguistic borrowing (Old English)”.

3 Gender in Middle English

Conventionally, the late Old English period ends in 1066. With the Battle of Hastings, Duke William II of Normandy -later know as William the Conqueror- defeated and killed Harold Godwinson, the last Anglo-Saxon king of England. The Middle English period therefore begins ca. 1100 AD and goes on until ca. 1470, when the printing press was introduced in England. The major figure writing in this vernacular was Geoffrey Chaucer, whose best known work are *The Canterbury Tales*²⁰ (ca. 1388).

While Old English texts predominantly adopted West-Saxon writing conventions (because of the political power of Wessex under king Alfred), Middle English manuscripts show a greater range of dialectal varieties. This is perfect to study the several coexisting alternatives which were present within the speech community (even though written language is more conservative and archaic than the spoken one).

3.1 From Old English to Middle English

In the transition period between late Old English and early Middle English the language underwent a massive change, especially from the morphological point of view. In fact, English experienced relatively abruptly three major linguistic developments (earlier in the North and then in the South):

- Obscuration and reduction of the vowels in the inflectional morphemes;
- Switch from a grammatical gender system to natural gender;
- Huge influx of loan-words, mainly from Scandinavian, French and Latin.

According to Curzan²¹, the gender system switch and the loss of inflectional endings (followed by an increased reliance on fixed word order) happened simultaneously, and are not one the consequence of the other.

Besides the gender system switch, on which we will focus later, what were the main consequences of the drastic morphological changes?

- Nouns came to distinguish only genitive and plural;
- The class of determiners was drastically simplified:
 - OE *se/seo/þæt* > *se/þeo* (already from LOE they were used without distinction of gender, case and number)

²⁰The image on the cover of this work is in fact a detail from the so-called *Ellesmere Chaucer*, an early 15th-century illuminated manuscript of Geoffrey Chaucer's *Canterbury Tales*, held in the Huntington Library, in San Marino, California (MS EL 26 C 9).

²¹A. Curzan (2003). *Gender Shifts in the History of English*. Cambridge University Press.

- se/þeo > ME the
- The deictic determiners came to be only number-distinctive:
 - singular: this, that
 - plural: thise/these, thos(e)
- The highly distinctive adjectives from OE turned into an unmarked class, with just the following endings surviving:
 - -e for the weak declension;
 - -∅ for strong singular;
 - -e for strong plural.
- Pronouns lost the distinction between accusative and dative forms, “she” was introduced to avoid confusion in the nominative forms, and the genitive was kept as it was:
 - Nom: OE he, heo, hit > ME he, she/sho, (h)it
 - Acc: OE hine, hie, hit > ME him, hire, hit/him
 - Gen: OE his, hire, his > ME his, hire, his
 - Dat: OE him, hire, him > ME him, hire, hit/him

It should be noted that this process didn’t take place overnight, nor did it happen uniformly in all England (as it was said before, the North was more advanced in this than the Midlands and the South, more conservative).

3.2 Switch from grammatical to natural gender

While the loss of morphological distinctions is unquestionably a critical component of the loss of grammatical gender, alone it is not enough to explain the shift between gender systems. In fact, other internal and external causal factors seem involved.

- **Internal reasons (system-based):**
 - In OE the gender of most nouns was not predictable from their form;
 - There were nouns with multiple gender;
 - The “Germanic stress rule”: the movement of stress toward the word-initial syllable (stress was variable in Proto-Indo-European).

Overall, many dialectal varieties existed, providing many variations of a particular feature. For a while, these can coexist, but eventually, some variants are chosen over the others by the speakers, whether for functional or for social reasons (e.g. prestige forms). One set of variants may be marked, but the two sets of forms may also be inter-changeable alternatives, at least until the older forms come to be seen as archaic. The progress of this replacement process often follows the traditional “S-curve” model for linguistic change.

- **External reasons (speaker-based):**

- Influence of Old Norse. In fact, Anglo-Saxons and Vikings farming and merchant communities were in close contact. The words of their languages were probably mutually intelligible at some level so that ON influenced OE from a grammatical point of view. Endings differed, so they were somehow “left out”, in order to avoid confusion between the cognate words’ usage.

This probably didn’t apply to German, and we could partly rely on this to account for its retaining of gender.

3.3 Gender in personal pronouns

The best way to account for the shift between a grammatical gender system to a semantic one, is through pronouns. Already in OE a strong pattern of natural gender agreement between nouns referring to humans and personal pronouns was found. In fact, with animates, sex-governed forms are the universal practice

even when gender conflicts with sex.²² e.g. *se wifman* (m.), *baet cild* (n.), *baet wif* (n.), and *baet bearn* (n.) can all be referred back with the feminine pronoun *heo* (Of course the conflict would have been only in singular forms, since plural pro-forms are not gender distinctive in English).

In contrast, for inanimate nouns grammatical gender is still upheld, as it is with nouns of animals, even though -as Clark²³ pointed out- the system “carried the seeds of its own decay”. This is particularly noticeable when there is a certain distance between the head and the pronoun, as we can see in the following example, from the Preface to the *Cura pastoralis*:

[...] *baet þu þone wisdom þe þe God sealde, þær þu hiene (m.)*
 [...] that you that wisdom which to-you God gave, there where you
 him (=it)
befaestan maege, befaeste. Gepenc hwelc witu us þa becomon
 implant may, implant. Think what punishments to-us then came
for þisse worulde, þa þa we hit nohwæþer ne selfe ne
 for this world, when we it neither ourselves
lufodon, ne eac oprum monnum ne lefdon [...]
 loved, nor other men allowed[...]

An example of the retaining of grammatical gender is the following:

Wið apan bite oððe mannes smyre mid fearres geallan. Sona heo bið
hal.
 For the bite of an ape or of a man, smear with a bull’s gall; soon it
 (=she) will be whole (healthy).

(*Quadrupedibus* 55)

Masculine inanimate nouns are affected first because of the reinterpretation of *his* and *him* as possible neuter forms in reference to masculine inanimate antecedents. In fact, the neuter dative form *him* is only gradually replaced by the objective form *hit*, and the genitive form *his* remains in use until in the 17th century *its* comes into use as the possessive form.

Note how the anaphoric pronoun used in the following sentence looks “normal” to our modern eye (*Hali Meidhad* 129):

[*þe deofles here of helle*] *weorrið & warpeð eauer towart tis tur forte*
keasten hit adun & drahen into þeowdom. þt stont se hehe þerin.
 [The devil’s army from hell] constantly attacks and throws toward
 this tower in order to cast it down and drag into slavery [the one]
 who stands so high therein.

²²Cecily Clark (1957). “Gender in the Peterborough Chronicle, 1070-1154”. In: *English Studies* 38, pp. 109–115.

²³Ibid.

Anaphoric pronouns referring to feminine inanimate antecedents shift to natural gender later than those referring to masculine antecedents. This means that it is generally grammatically acceptable to refer to inanimate nouns with feminine pronouns longer than it is generally acceptable to do so with masculine pronouns. Nonetheless, we can find attestations (even though they are still marked) of the modern usage already in Middle English:

*Hwen two beoreð a bur ðerne. E̅ te oþer leaueð hit; þenne mei þe þe
up haldeð hit felen hu hit wieið.*

When two bear a burden and the one leaves it, then the one who
holds it up can feel how it weighs.

(*Ancrene Wisse* 119)

In the following example no matter whether the antecedent noun is a grammatically feminine needle or a grammatically masculine awl or both, by early Middle English, it is more likely to be a neuter *hit*:

*A wummon þe haueð ilosed hire nede. oð er a sutere his eal. secheð
hit ananriht E̅ towent euch strea aþet hit beo ifunden.*

A woman who has lost her needle, or a shoemaker his awl, searches
for it immediately and turns over every straw until it is found.

(*Ancrene Wisse* 166)

As we can see from the last example –in agreement with the graph– the shift is now complete: the neuter pronoun has taken over the previously used masculine and feminine ones to refer to inanimate objects.

4 Gender in Modern English

From 1470 to about 1650 we talk of early Modern English, which is the language William Shakespear used. The Great Vowel Shift created a new phonology, while also grammar and spelling changed notably, comparing to Middle English. Notable differences are –just to name a few– the disuse of the T-V distinction (*thou, ye*) and the abolition of the letter *thorn* (*þ*) in writing.

Modern standard English has “pronominal gender”²⁴. The following scheme clearly explains the reason of Corbett’s definition, also known as the “normative pattern”²⁵. The 3rd person pronouns are used in the following way:

- NP [Male reference] ↔ He [“Masculine”]
- NP [Female reference] ↔ She [“Feminine”]
- NP [Non-personal reference] ↔ It [“Neuter”]

But, just like we have seen earlier for OE, Modern English has an “intimate pattern”²⁶, which relies on the point of view (perspective) of the speaker, disregarding the defining criteria of the normative pattern. It has of course to be considered a marked gender usage, difficult to distinguish from regional and dialectal variation and often influenced by the sex of the speaker.

4.1 Animation and reification

According to Mathiot²⁷, *animation* consists in “upgrading” the reference in order to satisfy the speaker’s wider purposes, such as for example signalling his/her attitude or relationship between discourse entities, or show emotional involvement or detachment.

There she blows!—there she blows! A hump like a snow-hill! It is
Moby Dick!

(*Moby Dick* by Herman Melville, 1851)

In his book, Pawley²⁸ draws the following conclusions (referred to Tasmanian Vernacular English and Los Angeles/Buffalo English varieties, which nonetheless suit our overview of gender in English’s history):

- The animated use of pronouns marks intimacy and informality;

²⁴Corbett, *Gender*.

²⁵Madeleine Mathiot and Robert Marjorie (1978). “Sex roles as revealed through referential gender in American English”. In: *Ethnolinguistics: Boas, Sapir and Whorf Revisited*. Ed. by Madeleine Mathiot. Mouton, pp. 1–47.

²⁶Ibid.

²⁷Ibid.

²⁸Pawley, “Using He and She for Inanimate Referents in English: Questions of Grammar and World View”.

- Non-standard usage is more frequent for men;
- Some inanimate referents can be referred to either as “he” or “she”;
- The choice of pronoun in such cases conveys some sort of affective information.

On the opposite side, there is *reification*, which we can state simply means “downgrading”. The inanimate pronoun *it* is associated with the unknown, the unemotional, the distant, the inferior and the despised. In fact, it bears a negative connotation if used in combination with animate references or may signify non-involvement and simple disinterest.

Charles: “Wednesday night?”

Camilla: “Oh, certainly Wednesday night. I’ll be alone, um, Wednesday, you know, the evening. Or Tuesday, while you’re rushing around doing things I’ll be, you know, alone until *it*²⁹ reappears.”

(*Camillagate*, an eight-minute tape of Prince Charles engaging in explicit conversation with his mistress, Camilla Parker Bowles, 18 December 1989)

²⁹Of course here the neuter pronoun refers to Camilla’s husband.

Conclusions

Germanic languages have evolved in very different ways if we consider them from the point of view of gender. German for example has been able to conserve its three-gender system, while North Germanic languages –such as Danish, Swedish and Norwegian– have fused masculine and feminine in a “common gender”, usually referred to as *uter* (in opposition with neuter). English instead, has undergone different passages: firstly a full grammatical gender system was in place. This was subject to what used to be seen as “incoherences”, but which are nowadays being explained as marked forms conveying different meanings. During the late Old English period and the early Middle English era though, grammatical gender was abandoned, in favour of natural gender. This had a semantic motivation, which better reflected the changed morphological system of Middle English. But also other factors were in play: as we have seen, the extension of natural gender to inanimate nouns seemed to coincide with a strengthening of the distinction between animate and inanimate nouns, for example. This is perfectly in line with the switch from a grammatical gender system to a natural gender system. Anyway this distinction is not yet complete: just think of the lack of an inanimate possessive relative pronoun in Modern English (for animates there is *whose*).

To conclude, we can state that “substandard” usages of gender can always be found and they should not surprise us at all. Gender variation is used by native speakers to convey “covert” pieces of information about what they think and on how they see the world.

References

- Clark, Cecily (1957). "Gender in the Peterborough Chronicle, 1070-1154". In: *English Studies* 38, pp. 109–115.
- Classen, E. (1919). "On the Origin of Natural Gender in Middle English". In: *The Modern Language Review* 14.1, pp. 97–102.
- Collins, J. D. (1990). "Natural Gender Vs. Grammatical Gender in Old English". In: *16th LACUS Forum*. Ed. by Linguistic Association of Canada and the United States, pp. 481–490.
- Corbett, Greville G. (1991). *Gender*. Cambridge Textbooks in Linguistics. Cambridge University Press.
- Curzan, A. (2003). *Gender Shifts in the History of English*. Cambridge University Press.
- Dekeyser, X. (1978). "The Diachrony of the Gender Systems in English and Dutch". In: *Historical Morphology*. Ed. by J. Fisiak. Mouton de Gruyter, pp. 97–111.
- Del Pezzo, Raffaella (1994). "Diacronia della lingua gotica?" In: *Annali Istituto Orientale di Napoli-Sezione Germanica* 4.1-2, pp. 9–22.
- Harris, A. C. and L. Campbell (1995). *Historical Syntax in Cross-Linguistic Perspective*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hockett, Charles F. (1958). *A Course in Modern Linguistics*. The Macmillan Company.
- Kitson, Peter (1990). "On Old English Nouns of More than One Gender". In: *English Studies* 71, pp. 185–221.
- Lazzeroni, Romano (2002). "Ruoli tematici e genere grammaticale: un aspetto della morfosintassi indoeuropea?" In: *Archivio glottologico italiano* 87.1, pp. 3–19.
- Luraghi, Silvia (2006). "La nascita del genere femminile in indoeuropeo". In: *Linguaggio e genere: grammatica e usi*. Ed. by S. Luraghi and A. Olita. Carocci.
- Mathiot, Madeleine and Robert Marjorie (1978). "Sex roles as revealed through referential gender in American English". In: *Ethnolinguistics: Boas, Sapir and Whorf Revisited*. Ed. by Madeleine Mathiot. Mouton, pp. 1–47.
- Pawley, Andrew (2002). "Using He and She for Inanimate Referents in English: Questions of Grammar and World View". In: *Ethnosyntax : Explorations in Grammar and Culture*. Ed. by N. J. Enfield. Oxford University Press, pp. 110–137.
- Schwink, Frederick W. (2004). *The Third Gender : Studies in the Origin and History of Germanic Grammatical Gender*. Winter.

- Vezzosi, Letizia (2008). “Come la linguistica generale e la tipologia possono aprire nuovi scenari: il caso dell’assegnazione del genere in anglosassone”. In: *La linguistica germanica oggi : bilanci e prospettive*. Ed. by Claudia Händl and Chiara Benati.
- Wehna, Jerzy (1980). “On gender change in linguistic borrowing (Old English)”. In: *Historical Morphology*. Trends in Linguistics. Studies and Monographs [TiLSM]. De Gruyter, pp. 399–420.